

DIAGNOSTIC PERSPECTIVES OF FISTULA IN ANO

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ABSTRACT

Fistula in ano is a common condition that occurs due to inadequate drainage or spontaneous bursting of a perianal abscess. It often recurs after best of surgery usually because of infection that was missed at surgery. Preoperative imaging can help identification of infection that would have otherwise gone unidentified. In particular, magnetic resonance (MR) imaging findings have been considered to influence surgery and markedly diminish the chance of recurrence according recent reports but in countries like India this is not possible for common patients to afford MR imaging because of cost effectiveness and availability of MRI equipment at common centres. Therefore, still fistulography is commonly used for preoperative imaging of fistula in ano. In this article fistula in ano and its imaging techniques are described, with an emphasis on fistulography by Deshpande technique.

A. FISTULA IN ANO

Anal fistulas, likewise referred to as fistula in ano a frequent ailment that, even after apparently successful treatment, tend to reoccur. Recurrences are typically the result of an infection that was missed after surgery and was left untreated. Well, it is reported in various research works that imaging prior to surgery, particularly magnetic resonance imaging (MR imaging), can be used to find abscesses and diseased tracts that could otherwise go undetected. Results from MR imaging prior to surgery has been demonstrated to impact following surgery and hence significantly reduce the risk after a surgical procedure and But keeping in view the condition of developing countries like India where majority of population lies below poverty line, an older economical imaging technique fistulography has been tried on 100 patients with fruitfull results. The method of imaging is not only cost effective but also can be carried out at small centres where MRI is not possible because of unavailaibility of equipments.

This review will cover the pathogenesis of ano fistula, how pathogenesis results in the many fistula forms that are encountered, and how these kinds can be imaged, with a focus on fistulography

Understanding the etiology of fistula and how anatomic boundaries characterize the different forms of fistulas is essential to comprehending the function of imaging in ano.

B. ANAL CANAL AND FISTULA IN ANO

The anal sphincters, internal and exterior, are made Comprising striated and smooth muscle, in turn, encircle the anal canal, which resembles a cylinder (Fig 1). The ligament anococcygeal is attached posteriorly to the external sphincter, while the urogenital diaphragm, the perineal body, and, in boys and men, the bulbocavernous muscle are attached anteriorly. The external sphincter merges proximally to form the anorectal junction, defined by the puborectalis muscle and subsequently with the pelvic floor's levator plate.

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Figure -1 shows the anatomy of the anal canal in the coronal plane. The letters EAS, IAS, IS, and LA stand for Levator ani, longitudinal muscle, internal and external anal sphincters, and puborectalis muscle, respectively.

The distal end of the gut tube's circular muscle is known as the internal sphincter. The purpose of the longitudinal smooth muscle of the rectal area, which interconnects internal and external digits sphincters, is likely to tie the anus together rather than having any clear sphincteric impact.

Located most commonly It is present as a film of fat with loose areolar tissue between the longitudinal muscle and the external sphincter is the gap between the sphincters, which is the area between the internal and exterior sphincters that is surgically dissected. Lying next to the sphincter complex laterally, the fat-filled ischioanal fossa is crossed by a web of fibers in fibroelastic connective tissue. The phrase fossa ischioanal is preferred by some authors to ischiorectal fossa, as this area primarily encircles the anus instead of the rectum. The two names can be used interchangeably, though. In terms of the nasal canal's lining, the proximal half is distinguished by longitude in al mucosal folds, Morgagni's anal columns. Each column's distal aspect is connected to its neighbour by the anal valves, a tiny semilunar fold that creates tiny compartments known as the anal sinuses, or crypts of Morgagni. The distal boundary of the anal transitional zone is shown by the dentate (pectinate) line, a histopathological connection between the anal squamous epithelium and the rectal columnar epithelium—is the distal undulating limit of these valves..

Since the crypts into which the anal glands empty are closest The dentate line is connected to the valves and is located roughly two centimeters away from the anal margin, is an important feature in fistula in ano. Chiari was the first to link these glands to the origin of fistula in ano, implying that they were the ones who site of contamination. Their function is unknown, but they might grease the anus with releasing mucous through the crypts of the anals. Anal glands' genesis in the tissues in the vicinity varies. As an illustration, they can be found within the sphincter internal and the subepithelium. Among these glands, one to two thirds are located deep within the intersphincteric region. According to the "cryptoglandular hypothesis," the majority of authorities believe that the initial cause of fistula in ano is contaminated with these glands called intersphincterics. Moreover, aggregation of lymphocytes encircle namely, the anal glands could help to explain why anal fistulas are more common in people with the illness Crohn's.

An intersphincteric abscess is thought to occur from gland infection if the drainage duct becomes clogged with infected debris. This abscess has two possible outcomes: it can spontaneously drain into the anal canal or it might worsen and become an acute anorectal abscess, which is frequently treated with urgent surgery. The most variable portion of the abscess is usually cut out and drained as part of the treatment; however, this technique ignores the infection source in the in tersphincteric space, so that up to 87% of individuals who suffer from an acute abscess may go on to develop a fistula. Therefore, it is generally accepted that an acute anorectal abscess and a fistula in ano are two different but equally severe symptoms of the same illness. In an effort to lower the frequency of subsequent fistula, the search for intersphincteric infection and an internal opening in the anal canal, followed by treatment of these at the time of acute presentation, have been recommended.

When an It is permitted for intersphincteric infection to worsen without treatment, fistula in the anterior develops. It primarily affects young adults and has an incidence of about 0.01%. Men are more likely than women to have fistula in ano, with a ratio of men to women of roughly 2:1. Men also predominate in all documented series. The majority of patients (65%) initially report with discharge, however inflammation-related local discomfort is also common. But some fistulas might not even cause any symptoms at all..

A fistula is an aberrant tube that joins two surfaces of the epithelium. Where the diseased Anal gland and the borders and planes of anatomy surrounding it will determine the anatomic course of an anal fistula. At the dentate line's level, or the original location the conduit that drains the diseased gland, there is typically an anal canal internal intestinal aperture. Due to the fact that Anal glands have more prevalent locations surrounding the anus that are radially posterior are mentioned with relation on a clock face, where the hour mark at 12 is immediately in front of—this is typically in the 6-o'clock position. There are several ways the fistula might access the perianal skin, some of which are more difficult to navigate than others.

Treatment is also mainly determined by classification. Anatomically speaking, the puborectalis muscle is known as the "anorectal ring." Milligan and Morgan classified fistulas are defined as openings above or below this structure that entered the anal canal. in 1934. They also warned that Should surgically split high fistulas occur without proper consideration, postoperative incontinence was likely to occur. Other writers went on to refine

and modify this classification, but Parks et al.'s, which thoroughly examined a sequential 400 patients in a row were sent to the surgeons at Hospital St. Mark's in London, England, is currently the most thorough and useful classification in use. Parks and colleagues discovered that they could categorize all fistulas into four distinct groups: extrasphincteric, suprasphincteric, transsphincteric, and intersphincteric. Importantly, the majority of

An intersphincteric fistula is formed when an intersphincteric infection festers along the intersphincteric space; in the Parks et al. series, this particular fistula accounted for 45% of cases (Fig. 2). It is significant that There is no fistula here pierce the a nearby sphincter external that creates a comparatively strong barrier against spread. Nonetheless, a few truculent fistulas are able to pass through the external restraint and arrive in the fossa of Ischioana in this manner (Fig 2). This causes a fistula transsphincteric, which occurred in 30% of the subjects in the Parks and others. Study there could be more fistulas. They must pass through the levator plate to get to the skin of the perianal, where they must arch over the puborectalis muscle and rise upward in the intersphincteric area. Twenty percent of individuals in the Parks et al. dataset had this form of fistula, known as a suprasphincteric fistula (Fig. 2)..

According to Parks et al., Figure 2 depicts the classification of ano Fistulas that are extrasphincteric, suprasphincteric, transsphincteric, and intersphincteric in the coronal plane.

In 5% of cases, Parks and colleagues additionally reported a fourth form of fistula. One notable feature of this kind was the unexpected lack of intersphincteric infection. Rather, the fistula made a direct entry into the rectum or anorectal junction (Fig 2). These were dubbed extrasphincteric fistulas by Parks et al. This type of fistula is obviously unrelated to Parks and anal gland infection et al. emphasized that when this type was observed, primary pelvic or rectal disease (such as Crohn's disease in the rectum and diverticular disease, or cancer) should be investigated. It should be highlighted that because of the specialized character of the St. Mark's Hospital, the Parks and others series unavoidably suffered from spectrum bias (a bias that Parks himself admitted). As a result, intricate fistulas were Most likely, overrepresented. For instance, Parks et al..

Even though the majority of fistulas most likely begin as a straightforward one main tract, an untreated infection may cause complications that branch off of this. The term "extensions" is typically used to refer to these supplementary tracts (Fig 3). Extensions' morphology could

point to tracts or abscesses. Extensions can be supralelevator (pararectal), ischioanal, or intersphincteric. Although the exact point at which a tract turns into an abscess is unclear, both phrases refer to infected areas. The most frequent location for an extension is the ischioanal fossa, particularly when it originates from the tip of a fistula transsphincteric (A in Fig 3). If there are extensions on both sides of the internal hole, they are referred to as "horseshoes" and also happen in the horizontal plane (Fig 3). Anatomical details of the route followed."

Figure 3.3: Fistula extensions, or secondary tracts, are depicted in the coronal plane: Extension A: from the transsphincteric apex fistula, into the Ischioanal Fossa's roof; B: from the apex of a supralelevator transsphincteric fistula pararectal extension; C: from the plane of intersphincters, supralelevator extension; D: from the horseshoe-shaped intersphincter.

The standard course of treatment entails making a surgical incision to expose the fistula, often by slicing into a metal probe that has been placed into the main tract. In fact, James Syme (1838) believed that opening a fistula was simple and questioned why the operation was carried out in a theatre "The entire show and fanfare of a major event," as the saying goes. Sadly, he was wrong; there are plenty of traps in store for the unsuspecting. A straightforward fistula can all too quickly become a surgical nightmare due to careless probing and improper incision, which would have catastrophic effects on the patient. The main goals are to completely clear the tract and remove any associated infection sites while also maintaining anal continence..

The craft of surgical fistulas is in striking the correct equilibrium between removal of infection and preservation of function. In order to accomplish these and these two surgical queries must be addressed prior to surgery: (a) How does the anal sphincter relate to the fistula (i.e., can the tract be left open safely with minimal chance of incontinence following surgery), and (b) are there any branches off the main tract that require treatment in order to avoid a relapse in order to prevent recurrence, and In that case, where are they situated?

To address these issues, surgeons have historically depended on examinations of patients who have received a general anesthetic, or examination under anesthesia (EUA). Using palpation to ascertain the fistula's link to the sphincter, the surgeon at EUA makes an attempt to categorize it. But anesthesia and the ensuing tone loss make it difficult to precisely identify the muscles beneath the surface. To locate the internal aperture, a metal probe is put into the

exterior opening and pointed in the direction of the dentate line. It's not as simple as it seems, either. For instance, when examining the anal canal, It might be necessary for the surgeon to inject hydrogen peroxide into the exterior orifice because the internal opening is typically hidden..

Another important factor is the peak of the internal aperture regarding the sphincters and anal canal; the greater the opening, the more sphincters will be separated. The majority of the surviving sphincter could be sacrificed, despite the fact that Morgan and Milligan recognized the significance as early as possible for continence of the puborectalis muscle 1934, saying, " However, if this ring is cut, control will undoubtedly be lost.." Nonetheless, it is now widely acknowledged that even slight sphincter division can result in functional impairment. Most importantly, careless questioning during an EUA can quickly lead to the creation of additional secondary tracts. For instance, vigorously penetrating the ceiling of the The Perhaps Ischioanal Fossa burst via the levator plate, resulting in a rupture into the rectum or perhaps a supralelevator extension that would create an extrasphincteric fistula. .

The key to healing the fistula is identifying the extensions at the EUA. It is commonly known that missed extensions—which in certain series have reached 25%—are the most frequent reason for recurrence. Extensions need special care and will always need more involved surgery. For instance, when supralelevator extensions are located high above the anal canal, they are particularly challenging to diagnose and treat because the levator plate prevents drainage.

As a result, confidently classifying the major tract at EUA can be exceedingly challenging, and there is plenty of room to exacerbate the situation. Individuals who have repeated illness are one specific example. These people are challenging to evaluate and have a higher likelihood of having undetected disease. The norm rather than the exception is multiple unsuccessful procedures, which means that scarring from repeated surgery and other causes is typically difficult to discern with digital palpation. Indurations because of a deeper extension. Moreover, it is more common for people in this category to possess prolongations that extend several centimeters beyond the main tract—frustratingly, in virtually any orientation, which makes it harder to detect the extensions. The related expansions typically get more complex the longer the fistula has been present. As a result, treating these patients inevitably becomes more challenging, and both the patient and the surgeon grow increasingly frustrated. Preoperative assessment that is accurate is essential to ending this cycle.

C. IMAGING FISTULA IN ANO: FISTULOGRAPHY

With varied degrees of success, radiologists have tried for many years to assist in addressing the surgical questions mentioned above. The first modality to be employed was fistulography boosted by contrast material. In order to characterize the fistula tract, a contrast agent soluble in water agent is gently filled with an external aperture using a small cannula during fistulography (Fig 4).

Figure- 4. Typical fistulography on a male individual. A coronal view makes it plain that the anorectal junction is surrounded by a number of high extensions, or arrows; nevertheless, because in this instance the pelvic floor, the levator ani—Not immediately seen, it is unclear where these are anatomically. In surgical management, defining the extension site (supra- or infralevator) is crucial.

Regretfully, There are two types of fistulography: Significant disadvantages. First, if expansions of the main tract are extremely far away, clogged with debris, or experience considerable contrast material backflow from the outside in orifice, they may not fill with contrast material. Secondly, the Since the sphincter muscles themselves cannot be clearly seen, the relationship It must be estimated between any tract and the sphincter. Moreover, it can be challenging to determine the presence of a supra- or infralevator in an extension position if the levator plate cannot be seen. Similar to this, it is frequently challenging to pinpoint the precise level of the anal canal's interior aperture precisely enough to assist the surgeon. As a result, fistulographic results are unreliable and challenging to interpret.

Due to the high mistake rate of this modality, Not much has been written about fistulography; Kuijpers and Schulpen; fistula in ano looked back over fistulographic pictures of 25 patients in an effort to estimate its worth. Only four (16%) of the subjects were found to have correctly comprehended and shown the internal opening and its accompanying extensions. Additionally, false-positive diagnosis Three patients (12%) had supralevator extensions and rectal holes made, which may have led to major surgical errors if they had been followed through on. They concluded—despite their past predisposition against the technique—fistulography was "unreliable and inaccurate." Weisman and colleagues, on the other hand, discovered that fistulography was more beneficial because it yielded meaningful data in more over half of the 27 participants inside their research.

It's been proposed that radiologists' lack of familiarity with the concepts of fistula pathophysiology, anatomy, and pertinent surgical problems is the main reason fistulography is typically ineffective. The diagnosis of a direct rectal opening based just on the presence of The rectal lumen contains contrast material. is one of the riskiest misinterpretations; in most cases, the agent of contrast has simply come up through the internal anal orifice. Like that radiological data can lead to iatrogenic secondary tracts by encouraging the surgeon to search for apertures and elongations that do not exist..

Inacceptability of fistulography technique has almost made this technique unreliable. But a

different technique of fistulography is in practice since long in Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi, Department of Shalya Tantra, Faculty of Ayurveda, Institute of Medical Sciences which is known as Deshpande technique. This technique is modification of Ahlback et al technique and is quite excellent in mapping of complicated fistulae. Ahlback et al (1974) mentioned that fistulography should always be done in relapsing and high anal fistulas. Diagnosis with help of fistulography can cause rectal fistula. New method of fistulography was adopted by them in 93 patients. A Clausen rectal catheter with a balloon and a solid rubber ball having 35 mm. diameters was taken. Balloon is inflated within rectum by which ball is pressed against the anus and anal canal is thus defined in between. Urograffin 60% is injected during fluoroscopy through a Nelaton catheter wide enough to occlude external opening of fistula. Full size films were taken in frontal, lateral and oblique projections. Clinically they classified fistula in ano into low anal, high anal and anorectal or pelvirectal varieties the boundry between low anal and high anal is the dentate line or pectinate line. This line is not demonstrable radiologically. They consider it to be 15mm above the anal opening. Boundary between high anal and pelvirectal is puborectal loop part of levator ani which is also not demonstrable. They considered it to be above 30mm above anal opening. Radiological findings are confirmed in 67 out of 93 cases. Deshpande et. al also devised a new technique which is almost similar to the method of Ahlback et al (1974) except that in place of solid rubber ball he used lead marker and condom in place of balloon.

Technique has been tried in 100 patients and following results have been drawn. Anatomical marking of the anal canal and rectum with the help of rectal catheter and condom helps to establish the relation of fistulous tarct with the rectum and internal canal of the anal launching and its location above or below the anorectal ring is identified with this technique. Ramificatios and cavitation and its relation to anal canal and rectum is located. Extent of fistulous tract can be identified. Communication with other viscera can be identified. (Fig-5 & 6)

Figure-(5). A & B showing fistulography by Deshpande technique. Here presence of gas shadow in the rectum filled in condom marks rectum, whereas rubber catheter in the canal of the anus marks the anal canal. Junction of the gas shadow and rubber catheter marks the anorectal ring level. External fistulous opening and anal verge is marked by lead marker.

(A)

(B)

Figure-(6). A & B showing fistulography by Deshpande technique. Here presence contrast agent over inflated condom shows internal opening and course of tract its relation with anal canal, anorectal ring and rectum is seen. Although anorectal ring is not imaged but it is assumed at meeting point of part of anal rubber tube and beginning of inflated part of condom. Lateral view shows cavitation at perirectal space.

D. IMAGING FISTULA IN ANO: CT

When rectal and intravenous contrast material are utilized, computed tomography (CT) can show fistula in ano, and preliminary results were positive. Still, accurate classification of fistulas is necessary; better and more current data indicate that CT cannot be utilized to this end with adequate accuracy. This is due to the fact that, unless the fistula itself includes air or contrast material, the CT attenuation of the anal sphincter and pelvic floor is comparable to that of the fistula itself. The inability to scan in the coronal plane, which is relevant for surgery, exacerbates this.

E. IMAGING FISTULA IN ANO: ANAL ENDOSONOGRAPHY

Clive Bartram, FRCP, FRCS, FRCR, invented anal endosonography, which was the first method to directly and thoroughly illustrate the anal sphincter complex. The transducer was able to be withdrawn through the anal canal by simply covering a rotating rectal endoprobe with a nondeformable plastic cone. This allowed the transducer to be positioned extremely close to the target structures, resulting in excellent spatial resolution images. The method's capacity to show the existence and degree of anal sphincter disruption, particularly following vaginal delivery, has drawn a lot of interest. Additionally, anal endosonography has been widely utilized for the preoperative categorization of anal fistulas.

Patients find the examination to be easy to undergo, quick, and comfortable. The patient is either prone if she is a female, or she is lying in the left lateral position. After being carefully placed into the distal rectum, the probe is removed via the anal canal. The exterior sphincter is of mixed echogenicity, while the internal sphincter is visible as a hypoechoic ring surrounding the anal canal (Fig 7). Between these are the intersphincteric space and longitudinal muscle, which are easily distinguishable with current 10-MHz transducers due to

their

mixed

echogenicity.

Figure- 7. Fistula intersphincterica. Anal endoscopy in the transverse plane at the mid-anal canal level in a male patient reveals an intersphincteric plane fistula with a hypoechoic tract situated between the internal (IAS) and external (EAS) anal sphincters. Sphincter internale is notably hypoechoic. Due to the fistula's radial location within the intersphincteric plane, the internal opening was accurately anticipated from anal endosonographic vision at the time of surgery, and it was located at 6 o'clock posteriorly.

F. IMAGING FISTULA IN ANO: MR IMAGING

When it comes to preoperatively classifying fistula in ano, MR imaging has become the most competitive option in recent years. The impact that magnetic resonance imaging (MR imaging) has had on surgical therapy and, ultimately, patient success is tangible. It has made it possible to precisely classify tracts and uncover diseases that would have gone unnoticed otherwise.

G. Technique

A specialized endoluminal anal coil yields the best spatial resolution; it can be used in conjunction with a surface coil to expand the field of vision. It should be mentioned that these endoluminal coils are intended to be inserted into the anus and have a smaller diameter than rectal coils. Typically, a plastic cover for the receiver coil permits it to be positioned across the anal canal (Fig 8). The exterior diameter typically falls between 12 and 19 mm, though investigations on children have occasionally employed smaller coils. Motion artifact is a possibility with endoluminal coils, however it can be minimized with good patient preparation. Patients should be instructed, for instance, to attempt to relax their pelvic floor and sphincter as much as possible. Comfort measures, such as providing the patient with pads and support for the coil, should also be taken into consideration. The use of spasmolytics, such as intramuscular injections of 1 mg of glucagon or 20 mg of hyoscine butylbromide, may help lessen motion-induced artifacts.

Figure- 8. MR imaging endoanal receiver coil.

H. MR Sequences

Diverse researchers have employed distinct approaches concerning the magnetic resonance sequences employed for imaging anos fistulas. They all use a technique to highlight infection (typically pus), and they all agree that anatomic precision is necessary to appropriately determine how the fistula is progressing in relation to surrounding tissues. There are several ways to accomplish these goals. A fast and convenient fast spin-echo T2-weighted sequence is used by many investigators because it allows for good discrimination between the various layers of the anal sphincter and good contrast between the hypointense fibrous wall of the fistula and the hyperintense fluid in the tract. Others have employed T1-weighted sequences, which need to be paired with intravenous contrast agent in order to highlight the fistula. Fat-suppression methods are commonly applied to T2-weighted and gadolinium-enhanced T1-weighted sequences (the latter may be particularly useful in Crohn's disease patients, to distinguish between hyperintense fluid and inflammatory tissue on fat-suppressed T2-weighted and/or short tau inversion-recovery [STIR] images between fluid and inflammatory tissue). All normal anorectal structures, including hemorrhoids, and the internal anal sphincter, do not significantly enlarge. Researchers have also effectively used a sequence called STIR, which combines high conspicuity of active tracts with fat suppression. Other methods have involved rectal contrast medium or saline instillation into the external orifice in an effort to improve tract conspicuity. But given the already good outcomes obtained with more conventional methods, such measures make the evaluation more challenging.

I. IMAGING PLANES

Accurate alignment of imaging planes with regard to the target organ—the anal canal—is essential for successful results. Due to a noticeable partial volume effect, straight transverse and coronal pictures will not align because the anal canal is angled forward from the vertical by about 45°. It is also important to create oblique transverse and coronal planes that are aligned orthogonal and parallel, respectively, to the anal sphincter. This can be done most readily with a midline sagittal picture (Fig 9). In difficult situations of an internal opening high in the rectum, it could be required to line follow-up tests with the rectal axis.

Figure- 9. Proper alignment for anal canal MR imaging. White lines indicate fully transverse pictures with respect to the anal canal that were planned using a sagittal T2-weighted scout image taken via the patient's midline. After that, coronal imaging is done at a 90-degree angle to the transverse plane.

It is crucial that the presacral region and a few millimeters above the levators—both of which are frequent locations for extensions—be included in the imaging volume. Include the entire perineum as well. Sometimes, tracts can reach the legs or even leave the pelvis, extending several centimeters. If a tract is evident and hasn't been included in the usual image volume, it needs to be followed all the way to its end (Fig. 10). When using an endoanal receiver, the entire sensitive area of the coil should be included in the imaged volume. Transverse pictures are typically the most useful for determining the exact location of the major tract (such as the ischioanal or intersphincteric tract); these images also make it easier to determine the radial placement of the internal opening. The levator plate is best shown in coronal pictures, which aid in differentiating supra- from infralevator infections. With the caveat that the anal canal must be scanned across its whole craniocaudal extent, coronal pictures may also be the best way to estimate the height of the internal aperture.

Figure -10 a: The coronal MR images obtained with an external phased-array coil exhibit a complex transsphincteric fistula with tract (short straight arrows) in the left ischioanal fossa that extends below ischial bone (I) toward the upper leg (not shown). Coronal (a) T2-weighted fast spin-echo (2500/70; echo train length, 16; field of view, 300 mm; matrix, 256 × 512; section thickness, 4 mm; gap, 0.4 mm) and (b) coronal STIR (4000/42, inversion time of 150 msec; echo train length, 16; matrix, 224 × 256; two signals acquired) MR images. Bone marrow edema (long straight arrow) at the ischial tuberosity is seen on b. Acute

opening = arrowhead, minor abscess = curved arrow, and anal sphincter = AS.

Figure-10b. The coronal MR images obtained with an external phased-array coil exhibit a complex transsphincteric fistula with tract (short straight arrows) in the left ischioanal fossa that extends below ischial bone (I) toward the upper leg (not shown). Coronal (a) T2-weighted fast spin-echo (2500/70; echo train length, 16; field of view, 300 mm; matrix, 256 × 512; section thickness, 4 mm; gap, 0.4 mm) and (b) coronal STIR (4000/42, inversion time of 150 msec; echo train length, 16; matrix, 224 × 256; two signals acquired) MR images. Bone marrow edema (long straight arrow) at the ischial tuberosity is seen on b. Anal sphincter (AS), curved arrow (small abscess), and arrowhead (external opening).

Even though the radial plane—which is rarely used to image the menisci of the knee—seems appealing, it can potentially show fistulas across their whole craniocaudal extent, something that typical coronal imaging can only accomplish when the fistula is at the 3- or 9-o'clock position. The picture planes are not obtained parallel to the anal canal; rather, they radiate from it in a manner akin to a wheel's spokes. The advantages of different imaging planes have not been well studied, although a transverse series combined with a longitudinal series (radial, coronal, sagittal, or a combination) offered all the information required for an accurate interpretation.

CONCLUSION

There is now overwhelming evidence that preoperative MR imaging changes the surgical technique and the extent of exploration and improves the final outcome in patients with fistula in ano who have a high likelihood of complicated disease in western countries. The most common cause of recurrent fistula in ano is an infection that was overlooked during surgical investigation. It is claimed that More accurately than any other modality, including surgical investigation, MR imaging shows remote sites of infection but in developing countries like India where MR imaging is not freely available and is cost effective too, Deshpande technique of fistulography and Anal endosonography is a good substitute for magnetic resonance imaging. The Deshpande technique is cheaper and needs only x-ray equipment along with some minor articles like rubber catheter, lead marker, condom and infant feeding tube which is freely available at smaller centres. Therefore this technique should be adopted for primary preoperative imaging of an anomalous fistula whereas anal endosonography and MRI analysis may be used at tertiary centres.

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